

Nurturing Resilient Learners In English: A Focus In Senior High School Teaching

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights of Senior High School teachers in nurturing resilient English learners within the Babak District, Division of IGACOS. Utilizing a qualitative phenomenological approach, the research examined the perspectives of eight Senior High School teachers. The findings revealed that teachers fostered resilience in English learners by cultivating a growth mindset, emphasizing adaptability and flexibility, and creating a supportive learning environment. To address challenges, teachers employed coping mechanisms such as promoting a growth mindset, maintaining a positive learning atmosphere, and adopting diverse teaching strategies. Educational insights highlighted the critical role of a positive learning environment, the promotion of a growth mindset, and the integration of real-world relevance in the curriculum. These elements were instrumental in nurturing resilience in English learners, contributing to their linguistic competence and the holistic development of adaptable, confident individuals prepared to navigate the complexities of an ever-evolving educational landscape. The study suggested that specialized teacher training programs focused on resilience-building strategies warranted further development and assessment for their impact on both teaching practices and student outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. resilient learners 2. senior high school teachers 3. Davao City, Philippines

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1. Introduction

In the realm of English education, the task of nurturing resilient learners stands as a pivotal undertaking, blending pedagogical expertise with an understanding of the psychological nuances involved in language acquisition. This multifaceted process extends beyond the traditional boundaries of language teaching, encapsulating the cultivation of an adaptive mindset essential for navigating the complexities of linguistic challenges. Nurturing the resilience of English learners involves fostering a belief that setbacks are not roadblocks but integral components of the language learning journey, each contributing to the development of proficiency and a resilient, growth-oriented mindset. In Malaysia, senior high school teachers play a crucial role in nurturing resilient learners in English through a multifaceted approach that combines pedagogical innovation with an understanding of the cultural and linguistic context. These educators often integrate student-centered and interactive teaching methodologies that emphasize real-world applications of the English language, aligning with the Malaysian education system's

emphasis on communicative language teaching (CLT) (Rahman, 2019). Additionally, the infusion of technology into English language education has become a prominent strategy among senior high school teachers in Malaysia. Leveraging digital tools and platforms not only enhances the engagement level of students but also reflects the nation's commitment to preparing learners for a technology-driven future (Kabilan et al., 2010). Through the incorporation of multimedia resources, online collaboration, and interactive learning platforms, teachers in Malaysia cater to the diverse learning preferences of students while simultaneously fostering adaptability and resilience in the face of evolving linguistic landscapes. In Japan, senior high school teachers employ a multifaceted approach to nurture resilient learners in English, combining traditional teaching methods with a focus on fostering a growth mindset and real-world applicability. Embracing the principles of Carol Dweck's Growth Mindset Theory (Dweck, 2006), teachers encourage students to view challenges as opportunities for learning and to understand that proficiency in English is a developmental process that involves persistence and effort. Senior high school teachers often integrate interactive and communicative language teaching methods, aligning with the Japanese Ministry of Education's emphasis on enhancing students' practical English communication skills (MEXT, 2021). Moreover, technology plays a significant role in nurturing resilient learners in Japanese high school English classrooms. Many teachers integrate digital tools and online resources to create dynamic and engaging lessons, promoting interactive learning experiences (Hayashi, 2018). This approach aligns with the Japanese government's efforts to incorporate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education (MEXT, 2021). In China, senior high school teachers cultivate resilient learners in English by integrating a combination of traditional teaching methods and innovative approaches that address the unique challenges of language acquisition. Embracing cultural and contextual considerations, educators emphasize the practical applications of English in various real-world situations, aligning with the communicative language teaching (CLT) approach (Li, 2019). Additionally, the integration of technology is increasingly prevalent in Chinese high school English classrooms, with teachers leveraging digital tools and online platforms to enhance language learning experiences (Wang He, 2017). This approach aligns with the Chinese government's emphasis on the importance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2017). In the Philippines, senior high school teachers foster resilient learners in English through a dynamic and culturally sensitive approach. Recognizing the diverse linguistic landscape of the country, educators often employ a communicative and interactive teaching style that emphasizes practical language use (Banawol, 2017). Teachers incorporate local contexts and real-life scenarios into lessons, making English relevant and applicable to the students' everyday experiences. By doing so, they instill resilience by showing that language proficiency is not just an academic pursuit but a practical skill that can empower students in various aspects of their lives. Moreover, the integration of technology is a growing trend in Philippine high school English classrooms. Senior high school teachers leverage digital tools, online resources, and multimedia platforms to create engaging learning environments (Paderanga et al., 2020). This approach aligns with the global shift towards digital literacy and enhances students' adaptability by exposing them to diverse technological resources. By incorporating these modern tools into language lessons, teachers not only enrich language skills but also nurture resilience by preparing students for effective communication in the digital age. In the local scenario particu-

larly in the senior high schools of Samal District, Division of IGACOS, senior high school teachers encountered a variety of experiences in nurturing resilient learners in English. Some of the experiences are enriching one, while others are negatively affect the teaching profession. It is in this context that this study was conceptualized to collect the experiences of senior high school teachers as they nurtured resilient learners in English. By delving into their rich narratives, we aim to uncover the multifaceted dimensions of this situation, the challenges encountered, and the remarkable impact it has on the senior high school learners.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to find out the experiences of senior high school teachers as they nurture resilient learners in English. Furthermore, it will serve as a reference material for future researchers in this area. Also, the results will throw more light on the experiences, mechanisms and insights drawn from the narratives of the informants.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intends to get the insights and the experiences of senior high school teachers as they nurture resilient learners in a changing world. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English?
- (2) How do senior high school teachers cope with challenges in nurturing resilient learners in English?
- (3) What educational management insights gained are drawn from the experiences of the informants?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Nurturing resilient learners in English- entails fostering the ability of students to adapt, persevere, and excel in the face of challenges within the realm of English language education.” Senior high school teachers - A senior high school teacher is an educator who teaches students in grades 11 and 12, preparing them for further education or career paths.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Officials. The findings of the study would give the DepEd officials, particularly in Samal district and the nearby senior high schools in the division of IGACOS and be aware on the different strategies in nurturing resilient learners in English. Senior high school Teachers. The study would be significant to them since they would know the issues and insights on their experiences as they nurture resilient learners in English. Stakeholders. This study would be significant to them since it would give the stakeholders the insights on how to assist school administrators in capacitating senior high school teachers on the strategies in nurturing resilient learners in English. Future Researchers. The findings generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future researches with similar or relevant scope.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—

This study is anchored on Social Cognitive Theory, proposed by Albert Bandura in 1986, emphasizes the dynamic interplay between individuals, their environment, and their behavior. In the context of nurturing resilient learners, this theory can help examine how senior high school teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and modeling of resilience influence students' development of coping skills and self-efficacy. It highlights the significance of observing and learning from role models, as teachers' narratives can serve as powerful examples of resilience in action. The theory also underscores the role of self-regulation and the ways teachers can empower students to take control of their emotions and responses to challenges, fostering a sense of agency and resilience. The second theory used in this study is Growth Mindset Theory by Carol Dweck's in (1990). Growth Mindset Theory is particularly relevant to a study on nurturing resilient learners. This theory proposes that individuals with a growth mindset perceive challenges as opportunities for learning and believe that intelligence and abilities can be developed through effort and dedication. Senior high school teachers, by actively promoting a growth mindset, can influence students' attitudes toward setbacks in English language learning. Encouraging students to view difficulties as a natural part of

the learning process can contribute to their resilience and willingness to persist in the face of linguistic challenges. The third theory used in this study is Cultural-Historical Activity Theory (CHAT) developed by Vygotsky in 20th century. It was further extended by Engeström, focuses on the sociocultural context of learning. In the context of senior high school English education, this theory would explore how the social and cultural aspects of the classroom environment shape students' resilience. It considers the interaction between individuals, tools, and the cultural context in the learning process. Understanding the cultural-historical context can provide insights into how language learning is influenced by the social dynamics within the classroom and the broader educational environment.

The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are three interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) Experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English; (2) coping mechanisms of senior high school teachers on the challenges in nurturing resilient learners in English; and (3) Educational insights gain from the experiences of the informants.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "The goal of this research worked

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research involves selecting the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action”, dealing with first principles, “ultimates,” or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how

the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English are discussed by the participants, and tries to investigate their coping mechanisms in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and

construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. It was made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The intention of this study was to gather information from the participants or senior high teachers in the Babak district Island Garden City of Samal in nurturing resilient learners in English. It is assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind

the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and mechanisms used in nurturing resilient learners in English. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtain from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the experiences of senior high school teachers as they nurture resilient learners in English.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English in Babak District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of se-

nior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological

research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience is a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and produc-

tive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the experiences and mechanisms used by senior high school teachers were explored and insights drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis related to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth

method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to investigate their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under

specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The

researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches are based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasize the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they are powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the senior high school teachers' experience and feelings in nurturing resilient learners in English, the researcher employed the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions would lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative

research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Eight (8) senior high school teachers from Samal District, Division of IGACOS. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) senior high school teacher; and (3) experienced in teaching English. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations

can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essen-

tial to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among senior high school teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that interests the researcher is the challenges senior high school teachers face in nurturing resilient English learners. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifi-

cations or questions with regard to the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members if they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The

study results were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and will be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which could be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview was carried out. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the necessary qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy

of Facilities. The researcher strived to ensure that the study could be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and re-

lated studies and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help to the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design,

making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are adequately secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant

research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are accurate to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study are presented through research questions – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, future directions and implications of the study are given by the researcher for the improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. The researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed to submit to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the study's objectives and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining con-

sent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher precisely transcribed the interviewees' responses by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data would then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the

participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were

compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the

researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data. A detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the

data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted,

and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher becomes aware of critical ideas and recurrent themes and makes a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may be unable to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used like interviews, documents, observations, The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes issues; however, it is at this stage that the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end,

the researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations were reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility involved establishing that the findings of the research were credible or believable from the perspectives of the participants. Ob-

serving the attributes of prolonged engagement is where credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job in describing the research context and assumptions that were relevant. On the other hand, dependability was

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the findings of the study were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability was the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other

researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and did rechecking of the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings were true and correct.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the study's research questions. The participants disclosed their teaching experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights into nurturing resilient learners in English. All these themes are discussed here.

3.1. Experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English—Nurturing resilient learners in the context of English education is a profound undertaking for senior high school teachers. This educational journey involved creating an environment that fosters linguistic proficiency and cultivates the mindset and resilience necessary for overcoming the challenges inherent in language learning. Senior high school teachers played a pivotal role in guiding students through these experiences, employing various strategies to instill a sense of adaptability, perseverance, and determination in the face of linguistic obstacles. Informed by contemporary educational theories and practices, this process draws in-

spiration from renowned psychologists such as Carol Dweck, whose work on mindset psychology emphasizes the transformative power of adopting a growth mindset in approaching challenges (Dweck, 2006). Additionally, incorporating feedback principles highlighted by researchers like John Hattie and Helen Timperley further contributes to creating a supportive learning environment that encourages students to view setbacks not as roadblocks but as opportunities for growth (Hattie Timperley, 2007). As educators navigate the complexities of nurturing resilient English learners, the integration of these experiences becomes essential for shaping students into adaptable and resilient individuals well-equipped for the demands of language education

3.1.1. Cultivated a growth mindset—Cultivating a growth mindset is a pivotal experience for senior high school teachers dedicated to nurturing resilient learners in English. This pedagogical approach, inspired by Carol Dweck's research on mindset psychology, centers on the belief that intelligence and abilities can be developed through dedication and effort (Dweck, 2006). This mindset shift is instrumental in shaping students' attitudes towards challenges and setbacks in English language learning. Dweck's seminal work underscores the idea that individuals with a growth mindset

perceive challenges as opportunities for learning and view effort as the path to mastery (Dweck, 2006). Armed with this understanding, senior high school teachers actively infuse their English teaching strategies with a growth mindset to foster resilience among their students. In the English classroom, senior high school teachers consciously praise students for correct answers, effort, perseverance, and strategies (Hattie Timperley, 2007). By emphasizing hard work and dedication, teachers guide students towards a mindset that views setbacks as stepping stones rather than insurmountable barriers.

ers. Senior high school teacher's adept at cultivating a growth mindset help students reinterpret challenges in English learning. Instead of seeing difficulties as indicators of a lack of ability, students are encouraged to see them as natural parts of the learning process. Through this reframing, teachers empower students to approach language challenges with resilience and a determination to improve. Leading by example, senior high school teachers exhibit resilient behavior in the face of their own challenges. Whether it's adapting lesson plans to better suit student needs or incorporating new

teaching methodologies, teachers demonstrate the application of a growth mindset in their professional lives, inspiring students to do the same in their English learning journey. Cultivating a growth mindset also involves creating a supportive classroom environment where students feel safe to take risks, make mistakes, and learn from them (Boaler, 2016). Senior high school teachers foster an atmosphere where students understand that their English proficiency is not fixed but can be developed over time with commitment and perseverance.

3.1.2. Emphasized Adaptability and Flexibility—Senior high school teachers emphasized the importance of adaptability and flexibility. By encouraging students to embrace change and be open to new ideas, teachers prepare them for a fast-changing world (Santos et al., 2021). Emphasizing adaptability and flexibility is a significant experience of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in a changing world. Teachers understand that the ability to adapt to new situations, embrace change, and remain flexible in the face of uncertainties is essential for thriving in an ever-evolving society. To instill these qualities in students, senior high school teachers design their lessons and learning experiences to incorporate diverse challenges that require adaptive thinking and problem-solving skills. By exposing students to a variety of learning scenarios and encouraging them to explore different approaches, teachers cultivate resilience and the capacity to navigate the complexities of a dynamic world (Santos et al., 2021). Moreover, senior high school teachers promote adaptability and flexibility through experiential learning activities.

These activities encourage students to step out of their comfort zones, engage in real-life situations, and learn to respond effectively to changing circumstances. Teachers design projects and simulations that mirror real-world challenges, enabling students to practice adaptability and make informed decisions in a safe and supportive environment (Chusri Khamwong, 2019). This experiential approach nurtures resilience as learners develop the confidence and skills to tackle novel situations and uncertainties with a proactive mindset. Furthermore, senior high school teachers themselves model adaptability and flexibility as they navigate the changing educational landscape. Teachers embrace new technologies, teaching methodologies, and approaches to meet the evolving needs of their students and the demands of a rapidly changing world (Jones et al., 2018). By demonstrating the value of adaptability in their own practices, teachers inspire and motivate students to adopt a growth mindset and view change as an opportunity for learning and growth. This emphasis on adaptability and flexibility empowers students to develop the resilience needed to succeed in an ever-changing world.

3.1.3. Developed a Supportive Learning Environment—Senior high school teachers prioritized creating a supportive and inclusive class-

room environment that fostered resilience in students. By providing a safe space for open communication, constructive feedback, and collab-

orative learning, teachers encouraged students to take risks, embrace challenges, and persevere in the face of difficulties (Levin, 2018). This positive learning environment enhanced students' confidence, motivation, and overall resilience, enabling them to thrive in a changing world. Cultivating a supportive learning environment is a crucial experience of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in a changing world. Recognizing the significance of emotional well-being in the learning process, teachers create a safe and inclusive classroom atmosphere where students feel valued, respected, and encouraged to express themselves freely (Jones et al., 2018). By fostering a positive teacher-student relationship, educators provide a support system that helps students cope with challenges, build self-confidence, and develop resilience. Teachers actively listen to students' concerns, offer constructive feedback, and celebrate their achievements, promoting a growth mindset that allows learners to view setbacks as opportunities for growth and improvement. Furthermore, senior high school teachers implement social-emotional learning (SEL) programs to cultivate resilience within their students. These programs provide opportunities for learners to develop self-awareness,

emotional regulation, and interpersonal skills, which are essential for navigating a changing world (CASEL, 2021). Through SEL, teachers empower students to recognize and manage their emotions, handle stress effectively, and build positive relationships with peers and teachers. This emotionally supportive learning environment enhances students' social and emotional well-being, contributing to their overall resilience and readiness to face life's challenges. Moreover, senior high school teachers encourage collaboration and teamwork in the classroom, fostering a sense of community among students. By promoting group projects, team activities, and peer interactions, teachers create opportunities for students to learn from one another, build empathy, and develop effective communication skills (Cheung Cheung, 2017). This collaborative atmosphere helps students feel connected and supported, enabling them to develop strong interpersonal relationships and resilience in the face of academic and personal challenges. Figure 3 shows the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English and the emergence of the three themes: cultivating a growth mindset, emphasizing adaptability and flexibility, and developing a supportive learning environment.

3.2. Coping mechanisms of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English—Navigating the challenges of English education in senior high school settings demands a nuanced understanding of the coping mechanisms teachers employ to foster resilience in their students. The journey of nurturing resilient learners involves transmitting language skills and equipping students with the tools to overcome obstacles and setbacks. Senior high school teachers, in this context, play a pivotal role in developing effective coping strategies that empower students to thrive in the intricate landscape of English language learning. Drawing insights from psychological theories, partic-

ularly those emphasizing coping mechanisms and resilience, teachers employ these strategies to guide students through the complexities of language acquisition. For instance, the work of researchers such as Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman, pioneers in the field of stress and coping, offers valuable insights into understanding how teachers can cultivate resilience by assisting students in developing adaptive coping mechanisms (Lazarus Folkman, 2004). As educators engage with these coping mechanisms, they not only fortify their students against the challenges of English education but also contribute to the broader goal of nurturing resilient individuals equipped for lifelong learning.

Fig. 3. The emerging themes on the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English

3.2.1. Promoting Growth Mindset—Promoting a growth mindset is a fundamental coping mechanism employed by senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English. Grounded in the pioneering work of psychologist Carol Dweck, a growth mindset is the belief that intelligence and abilities can be developed through effort and dedication (Dweck, 2006). This pedagogical approach is crucial in the context of language learning, as it encourages students to perceive challenges as opportunities for growth, fostering resilience in the face of linguistic difficulties. Dweck’s research emphasizes the importance of understanding the difference between a fixed mindset, where individuals believe their abilities are innate and unchangeable, and a growth mindset, where individuals view challenges as opportunities for learning and growth (Dweck, 2006). Senior high school teachers, armed with this understanding, actively promote a growth mindset among their students in the English classroom, guiding them to embrace challenges with the belief that effort and perseverance lead to improvement. Promoting a growth mindset involves more than just praising correct answers; senior high school teachers consciously commend students for their effort, perseverance, and strategies employed in the learning process (Hattie Timperley, 2007). By shifting the focus from in-

nate abilities to the value of hard work, teachers contribute to developing resilience in English language learning. In the English classroom, senior high school teachers actively encourage students to view challenges not as indicators of a lack of ability but as natural aspects of the language learning journey. This reframing is pivotal in cultivating resilience as students begin to approach linguistic difficulties with a growth-oriented mindset, recognizing that overcoming challenges contributes to their overall development. Fostering a growth mindset also involves creating a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable taking risks, making mistakes, and learning from them (Rimm-Kaufman et al., 2009). Senior high school teachers establish classrooms where students understand that making errors is an integral part of the learning process and an opportunity for improvement. Promoting a growth mindset in the English classroom profoundly impacts creating resilient learners. Students who embrace a growth mindset are more likely to persist in the face of setbacks, seek out challenges, and exhibit a positive attitude toward learning (Dweck, 2006). This coping mechanism, therefore, becomes an essential tool for senior high school teachers in nurturing students who are not only proficient in English but also resilient individuals equipped for lifelong learning.

3.2.2. Cultivating Positive Learning Environments—Cultivating a positive learning environment serves as a crucial coping mechanism for senior high school teachers striving to nurture resilient learners in English. This approach recognizes that the classroom atmosphere significantly impacts students’ emotional well-being, motivation, and ability to navigate linguistic challenges effectively. Informed by educational research and the work of psychologists, senior high school teachers actively shape environments that promote positivity and sup-

port. Research by Rimm-Kaufman et al. (2015) highlights that positive learning environments contribute to students’ engagement and academic success. In the context of English education, this involves creating a space where students feel safe to express themselves, take risks in language learning, and collaborate with peers. Such an environment becomes a foundation for resilience, as students are more likely to approach challenges with a positive mindset. Cultivating a positive learning environment involves emphasizing psychological safety. Se-

Senior high school teachers strive to create classrooms where students feel secure in expressing their thoughts and opinions without fear of judgment. This psychological safety fosters an atmosphere where students are more willing to engage with challenging English concepts, knowing that mistakes are viewed as opportunities for growth (Edmondson, 1999). Research by Wang and Eccles (2012) underscores the importance of a sense of belonging in academic settings. Senior high school teachers actively work to create a community within the classroom, where students feel a sense of belonging and connection. This sense of community reinforces resilience, as students are more likely to persevere through challenges when they feel supported by their peers and teachers. Cultivating positive learning environments involves the strategic use of positive reinforcement. Senior high school teachers recognize and celebrate students' achievements, both big and small, fostering a culture where success is acknowledged and effort is appreciated. This positive reinforcement contributes to

building students' confidence and resilience in their English language learning journey (Hattie Timperley, 2007). Promoting collaboration is a key aspect of cultivating a positive learning environment. Senior high school teachers structure activities that encourage students to work together, fostering teamwork and shared problem-solving. Collaborative learning experiences not only enhance language skills but also contribute to the development of resilience as students learn to navigate challenges collectively (Thomas, 2000). The creation of a positive learning environment is intertwined with promoting a growth mindset (Dweck, 2006). Senior high school teachers actively encourage students to view challenges as opportunities for learning and emphasize the importance of effort in the language learning process. By fostering a growth mindset, teachers contribute significantly to the development of resilient learners who approach linguistic challenges with a positive and adaptive mindset.

3.2.3. Adapting Teaching Strategies— Adapting teaching strategies is a fundamental coping mechanism employed by senior high school teachers in the pursuit of nurturing resilient learners in English. In the dynamic landscape of education, the ability to flexibly adjust instructional approaches is essential to address the diverse needs and challenges students encounter in their language learning journey. Senior high school teachers acknowledge the diversity in learning styles among their students and adapt their teaching strategies accordingly. This recognition, supported by educational research (Tomlinson, 2017), allows teachers to tailor their approaches, ensuring that students with different preferences and strengths have opportunities to excel in the English language. An integral part of adapting teaching strategies involves being responsive

to student feedback. By creating an open and communicative environment, senior high school teachers can understand the specific challenges students face and make adjustments accordingly (Hattie Timperley, 2007). This responsiveness enhances the effectiveness of language instruction and contributes to the development of resilient learners. Adapting teaching strategies also involves leveraging technology to enhance language learning experiences. Senior high school teachers incorporate educational tools, online resources, and interactive platforms to engage students in ways that resonate with their digital-native tendencies, contributing to a more dynamic and adaptable learning environment. Differentiated instruction is a key aspect of adapting teaching strategies. This approach, supported by educational theorists like Carol Ann Tomlinson (2017), ensures that senior high

Fig. 4. The emerging themes on the coping mechanisms of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English

school teachers tailor their lessons to accommodate the diverse learning styles, abilities, and interests of their students, promoting inclusivity and resilience. Maintaining flexibility in lesson planning allows senior high school teachers to adapt to the evolving needs of their students. Whether through adjusting the pace of instruction, incorporating additional practice, or introducing alternative resources, this adaptability demonstrates a commitment to fostering resilience by addressing challenges in real time. Adapting teaching strategies extends to embracing innovative pedagogies that align with the

changing educational landscape. Senior high school teachers explore and incorporate new methodologies, such as project-based learning or flipped classrooms, to provide students with varied and engaging approaches to language acquisition, contributing to a more resilient and adaptable learning experience. Figure 4 shows senior high school teachers' coping mechanisms in nurturing resilient English learners and the emergence of three themes: promoting a growth mindset, cultivating a positive learning environment, and adapting teaching strategies.

3.3. *Insights gained from the experiences of senior high school teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English*—The insights gained from the experiences of senior high school

teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English offer a profound understanding of the dynamic interplay between pedagogy, psychology, and student development. By delving into

the challenges faced and strategies employed by these educators, a rich tapestry of effective methodologies and impactful interventions emerges. This exploration not only sheds light on the intricate process of language education but also provides valuable lessons for educators, policymakers, and researchers seeking to enhance the resilience and proficiency of learners. Drawing from seminal works in education,

3.3.1. Importance of Positive Learning Environment—The experiences of senior high school teachers underscore the paramount importance of cultivating a positive learning environment in nurturing resilient learners in English. This environment serves as a foundational element, providing the emotional and psychological support necessary for students to navigate the complexities of language learning. According to Rimm-Kaufman et al. (2015), a positive learning atmosphere contributes significantly to students' engagement, creating a sense of security that fosters resilience. Senior high school teachers emphasize that when students feel supported and encouraged, they are more likely to approach linguistic challenges with a positive mindset, seeing setbacks not as roadblocks but as stepping stones to improvement. A positive learning environment encourages students to take risks and make mistakes, which are inherent aspects of the language learning process. Senior high school teachers recognize the insights gained from creating classrooms where making errors is viewed as a natural part of learning (Rimm-Kaufman et al., 2009). By destigmatizing mistakes, teachers empower students to push beyond their comfort zones, fostering resilience as students learn to persevere through challenges and view setbacks as opportunities for growth. Insights gleaned from the experiences of senior high school teachers highlight the role of a positive learning environment in building a sense of belonging. When stu-

psychology, and language acquisition, these insights underscore the importance of a holistic approach that encompasses differentiated instruction (Tomlinson, 2017), constructive feedback (Hattie Timperley, 2007), and the cultivation of a growth mindset (Dweck, 2006) as pivotal elements in shaping resilient English learners.

dents feel connected to their peers and teachers, they are more likely to seek help when needed, collaborate on language tasks, and share their thoughts without fear of judgment (Wang Eccles, 2012). This sense of belonging contributes significantly to the resilience of learners, creating a supportive community within the classroom. Positive learning environments are conducive to building strong teacher-student relationships, another crucial insight. According to Hattie and Timperley (2007), the power of feedback is amplified when students have positive relationships with their teachers. In the context of English education, this means that constructive feedback is more readily accepted and utilized by students when there is a foundation of trust and positive rapport between teacher and learner. Senior high school teachers emphasize that a positive learning environment extends beyond academic considerations to encompass the emotional well-being of students. Brackett and Katulak (2007) highlight the importance of emotional intelligence in the classroom, and teachers who prioritize creating a positive atmosphere contribute to students' emotional resilience. By integrating emotional support into the learning environment, teachers enhance students' abilities to manage stress, setbacks, and the emotional challenges associated with language learning. The insights gained from senior high school teachers' experiences stress that the benefits of a positive learning environment extend beyond the immediate academic setting.

Wang and Eccles (2012) note that a positive school environment has longitudinal effects on students' engagement. Senior high school teachers recognize that by nurturing resilient learners

3.3.2. Growth Mindset Promotion—Insights gained from the experiences of senior high school teachers highlight the pivotal role of promoting a growth mindset in nurturing resilient learners in English. Rooted in the work of Carol Dweck (2006), a growth mindset fosters the belief that intelligence and abilities can be developed through dedication and effort. Senior high school teachers emphasize that instilling a growth mindset serves as the foundation for academic resilience in the face of linguistic challenges. Students who embrace this mindset approach obstacle in language learning not as insurmountable barriers but as opportunities for growth and improvement. One key insight is the transformative power of framing challenges as learning opportunities. Senior high school teachers actively promote the idea that setbacks and difficulties in English language acquisition are integral to the learning process. By cultivating a growth mindset, students learn to view mistakes not as indicators of incompetence but as stepping stones toward mastery (Dweck, 2006). This shift in perspective is fundamental to building resilience, as learners become more willing to tackle complex language tasks with an understanding that effort and persistence lead to improvement. Promoting a growth mindset contributes significantly to shaping positive attitudes towards language learning. Senior high school teachers observe that students with a growth mindset are more likely to approach English lessons with enthusiasm and curiosity.

3.3.3. Real-World Relevance—Insights gleaned from the experiences of senior high

in English within a positive context, they are instilling attitudes and skills that contribute to a lifelong love of learning and adaptability.

Dweck's research (2006) suggests that fostering a belief in the malleability of intelligence contributes to a love of learning and a willingness to embrace linguistic challenges, reinforcing the idea that resilience is closely tied to one's mindset. Insights underscore the importance of emphasizing effort over innate ability in language education. Senior high school teachers actively work against fixed mindset beliefs that may limit students' willingness to engage with difficult English concepts. By praising and reinforcing the effort students put into their language learning, teachers contribute to the development of resilience by shifting the focus from perceived innate ability to the value of dedication and perseverance (Hattie Timperley, 2007). A growth mindset promotes the development of perseverance and determination in students. Senior high school teachers note that students who believe in their capacity to improve through effort are more likely to persist through challenges, setbacks, and the inherent complexities of language acquisition. This insight aligns with research emphasizing the link between perseverance and academic success (Dweck, 2006). The experiences of senior high school teachers highlight that the promotion of a growth mindset has a lasting impact on students' learning skills beyond the English classroom. Students who internalize a growth mindset are better equipped for lifelong learning, as they carry the belief that they can adapt, learn, and improve throughout their educational journey and beyond (Dweck, 2006).

school teachers emphasize the significance of integrating real-world relevance into English

language education. Teachers provide students with a contextual understanding of English by bridging the gap between theoretical language concepts and practical applications. This insight aligns with the research emphasizing the effectiveness of connecting classroom learning to real-world scenarios (Boaler, 2016). Senior high school teachers observe that when students see the real-world relevance of their English studies, they are more likely to engage with enthusiasm and resilience, understanding the tangible impact of language skills in their lives beyond the classroom. The integration of real-world relevance serves as a powerful motivator for learners. Senior high school teachers note that motivation increases when students understand how English language skills are directly applicable to their lives. Boaler's work (2016) emphasizes the importance of inspiring learners by showcasing the real-world applications of academic content. In English education, this translates into students recognizing the practical utility of language skills in communication, problem-solving, and navigating various life situations. Bridging the gap between theory and practice is about making sure what you learn in books, classes, or training can be effectively used in real-life situations. Here is how you can make this connection more assertive, whether studying, working, or applying new skills in your everyday life. Senior high school teachers' insights highlight real-world relevance's role in enhancing intrinsic motivation among learners. When students perceive the direct connection between what they are learning and real-world situations, their interest and curiosity are naturally sparked (Boaler, 2016). This intrinsic motivation becomes a driving force in the face of language learning challenges, fostering resilience as students actively seek to improve

their English skills for meaningful, real-world applications. The incorporation of real-world relevance into English education cultivates critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Senior high school teachers note that when students engage with language in authentic, real-world contexts, they are prompted to think critically about how to apply their knowledge (Thomas, 2000). This deepens their understanding of English concepts and equips them with adaptive problem-solving skills, contributing to overall resilience in language learning. Real-world relevance provides a crucial insight into the importance of connecting English learning to students' lives. Senior high school teachers find that when language lessons resonate with students' experiences and aspirations, the relevance enhances their sense of purpose in language acquisition. This connection fosters resilience as students see English not just as an academic subject but a tool for personal and professional growth, motivating them to overcome challenges. The experiences of senior high school teachers suggest that the integration of real-world relevance has a long-term impact on students' retention and application of English skills. By emphasizing practical applications, teachers contribute to the development of learners who not only master language concepts but also retain the knowledge for future use. This insight aligns with the idea that real-world connections facilitate a deeper and more enduring understanding of academic content (Boaler, 2016). Figure 5 shows the educational management insights gained from the informants' experiences and the emergence of the three themes: the importance of a positive learning environment, the promotion of a growth mindset, and real-world relevance.

Fig. 5. Educational management insights gained from the experiences of the informants

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study was presented, and from the summary of the findings, the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to solicit the experiences of Senior High School teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English in Samal District, Division of IGACOS. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—The study's findings on teachers' experiences in nurturing resilient learners in English revealed that a cultivated growth mindset, emphasis on adaptability and flexibility, and the development of a supportive learning environment were necessary. The teachers' coping mechanisms for nurturing resilient learners in English were disclosed as promoting a growth mindset, cultivating a positive learning environment, and adapting teaching strategies. Regarding the educational management insights gained from the participants, the teachers emphasized the importance of a positive learning environment, growth mindset promotion, and real-world relevance.

4.2. Implications—The results of my study uncovered the following significant findings. Based on teachers' experiences in nurturing resilient learners in English, results revealed the following themes: First, cultivated mindset. It centered on the belief that intelligence and abilities can be developed through dedication and effort. This mindset shift is instrumental in shaping students' attitudes towards challenges and setbacks in English language learning. Second, it emphasized adaptability and flexibility. By encouraging students to embrace change and be open to new ideas, teachers prepare them for a fast-changing world. Exposing students to various learning scenarios and encouraging them to explore different approaches cultivate resilience and the capacity to navigate the complexities of a dynamic world. Third, develop a supportive learning environment. Teachers encouraged students to take risks, embrace challenges, and persevere in the face of difficulties by providing a safe space for open communication, constructive feedback, and collaborative learning. On the coping mechanisms of teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English, one of the themes that was shown was promoting a growth mindset. It encouraged students to perceive challenges as opportunities for growth, adopting resilience in the face of linguistic difficulties. Fostering a growth mindset also involved creating a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable taking risks, making mistakes, and learning from them. The second theme identified was cultivating a positive learning environment. Cultivating a positive learning environment recognizes that the classroom atmosphere significantly impacts students' emotional well-being, motivation, and ability to navigate linguistic challenges. Positive learning environments contribute to students' engagement and academic success. The third theme was adapting teaching strategies. The ability to flexibly adjust instructional approaches was essential to address the diverse needs and challenges students encounter in their language learning journey. Adapting teaching strategies also involves technology to enhance language learning experiences. Incorporation

of educational tools, online resources, and interactive platforms to engage students in ways that resonate with their digital-native tendencies, contributing to a more dynamic and adaptable learning environment. The first theme identified in the educational management insights gained from the teachers in nurturing resilient learners in English was the importance of a positive learning environment. A positive learning atmosphere contributed significantly to students' engagement, creating a sense of security that promotes resilience. The second theme identified was growth mindset promotion. Instilling a growth mindset was the foundation for aca-

demically resilient in the face of linguistic challenges. Students who embraced this mindset approached obstacles in language learning not as insurmountable barriers but as opportunities for growth and improvement. The third theme was real-world relevance. This emphasized the significance of integrating real-world relevance into English language education. Teachers observed that when students see the real-world relevance of their English studies, they are more likely to engage with enthusiasm and resilience, understanding the tangible impact of language skills in their lives beyond the classroom.

4.3. Future Directions—This study may provide an avenue for future researchers to take diverse paths to enhance their understanding of implementing strategies that foster resilience. One potential avenue is integrating technology within language learning, exploring how digital tools and platforms could create adaptive environments that promote persistence and problem-solving skills. Moreover, specialized teacher training programs focused on resilience-building strategies could be further developed and assessed for their impact on teachers' practices and student outcomes. The cultural dimensions of resilience in English language learn-

ers also merit attention, prompting studies investigating the influence of cultural sensitivity and inclusivity on resilience levels. Another promising direction involves exploring the role of literature and creative writing in promoting emotional intelligence and perseverance among English learners. Assessment tools tailored to measure resilience in language learners and investigations into the impact of community engagement on resilience constitute additional avenues for future research. By delving into these areas, researchers can contribute nuanced perspectives to the ongoing discourse on nurturing resilient learners in the English language.

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